

THE ROLE OF THE MEDIA IN INCREASING MEDIA LITERACY OF THE POPULATION

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Abstract. *This article is about the role, importance and relevance of media in increasing media literacy among the population. There are several recommendations, opinions and questionnaires on increasing the media literacy of today's youth. Also, within the framework of this topic, the research of domestic and foreign researchers was studied and analyzed from a psychological point of view.*

Keywords: *media literacy, media education, media competence, education, media competence criteria, media.*

The term “media” comes from Latin - medium, that is, a means, an intermediary, a means of communication and information in various forms. The content of the concept of media includes the means of creating, copying, and distributing information, as well as the technical means of information exchange between authors and the public audience [1]. Information literacy refers to a set of skills and competencies in the selection, evaluation, processing and transmission of information. Information literacy recognizes the importance of owning, evaluating, and using information ethically.

Today, there are several approaches to studying modern media texts. Researchers call mediatization as the most important sign of modern civilization. The result of mediatization is the formation of a media reality or a media picture of the world that cannot help people, especially children and adolescents whose worldview is not yet fully formed. Modern mass media are used in all areas of human life; it also affects the processes in the field of culture and education. The growing flow of information requires a person not only to adequately perceive and effectively process information, but also to creatively understand and critically analyze media messages[2]. From this point of view, the goal of media education as an integral part of modern education is the formation of media competence of a person.

Media and information literacy in the modern world are a set of skills, abilities that allow users to analyze media messages broadcast through the media and the Internet, the ability to critically approach the received data and perceived information. The development of information literacy is closely related to the acquisition of digital and media competencies. The ability to think critically and not to trust all information that is distributed on the network, and above all to analyze the data base, assess the status of the media and the author are the main components of a person's media literacy. The materials of our research are books and scientific articles on media literacy, the development of media literacy and critical thinking skills in modern society, as well as Internet sites. The methodology is based on fundamental research in the field of interconnection and integrity of phenomena, logical cognition, information literacy theory and development trends of modern society. The research is based on comparative analysis.

The above data, on the one hand, determine and confirm a real increase in the time people spend at work and communication through the information and communication capabilities of the Internet, and on the other hand, they show that people do not possess all the tools necessary for information literacy and the development of critical thinking, as well as software products necessary for distant work and data analysis[3].

Modern media technologies provide a person with huge potential opportunities for information exchange, “virtual” acquaintance with different countries and their culture, expansion of worldview, and improvement of the professional and general cultural level of a person. However, at the same time, the expansion of the mass media leads to the excessive spread of personal information, psychological manipulative effects, “virtualization of the mind” and the strengthening of stereotypes in interpersonal communication. This requires increasing media education and media literacy. Not only does the journalistic community demand a more adequate approach to social media reporting, but they also demand an audience of intelligent readers who have mastered at least the basics of media literacy. The “fake news” epidemic puts the media with the task of restoring trust to an audience that increasingly prefers to get information through social media.

Y. Lipshits said that for several years media literacy has been the subject of scientific debate, but despite this, there is still no single answer to the questions of what is media and information literacy, its content and what specific skills should be developed [4].

In his work, A. Hippel studied the ideas of seniors about the concept of media competence, brought a significant difference in the understanding of media competence by adults and revealed this concept in accordance with their profession[5].

Taking into account the role of mass media in modern society, researchers and the public are increasingly paying attention to the need to develop media education in preschool education, school and university at all levels of education. Media literacy and media competence are important for almost all educational fields today. In addition, mass media is considered an integral part of education.

It should be noted that the structure of a person's media competence is complex and includes “mental formations” that describe a person's needs for mass media, his media preferences, the level of orientation to the media world, as well as the level of formation. At the same time, it should be noted that media literacy or media competence should not be seen in terms of people's level of knowledge, but in a broader context that covers areas of life such as civil society. Taking into account the above, a media literate person is considered to be a person who understands various aspects of media activities, i.e. socio-cultural, economic and political, and has sufficient skills to perceive media materials of different formats and genres on different media platforms [6]. A media-literate person not only knows how to separate opinion from fact, manipulation from objective information, but also has a strong civic stance and responsibility.

Due to the deep penetration of media literacy and information culture into our lives, the volume of information has also increased and is the best guarantee of public democratic dialogue in such a global process. This type of communication is a key factor in the realization of human rights. All events and processes in the world can shed light on one or another historical source in a unique way and at the same time be the reason for the discovery of important historical information[7]. Philosophy, cultural studies, ethnology, ethnography, art history, sociology and other similar disciplines are leading in the study of past history, social and humanitarian sciences.

However, in essence, it is an important component of the history of science. If we turn to historical sources, we will learn that primitive man tried to express his thoughts with the help of various signs and images that he invented. There is an argument that the language, writing and form of communication, which are important in human life, appeared in this way[8]. If we want to think about the history and evolution of language, we need to study it scientifically.

An abundance of misinformation erodes public trust in the media. The analysis of the collected data showed that the youth audience tends to increase their media literacy, moreover, the audience without journalistic skills perceives information sources and their potential reliability differently than professional journalists. First of all, we need to improve our media literacy so that we do not believe in false information. If we teach a child to distinguish between what is good and what is bad, as well as white and black, if we expand the scope of thinking, increase his literacy, make him knowledgeable and intelligent, then the child will not fall into the clutches of any false information and get lost.

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